

A Kinetic Study of the Reaction of Diethyl Phosphite with Mercuric Acetate

W. I. AWAD, M. EL-DEEK and E. EL-SAWI

Department of Chemistry, University College for Women and Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt

Manuscript received 12 April 1977, accepted 29 July 1977

The reaction of diethyl phosphite with mercuric acetate to form the mercurated phosphorus compound (2) has been studied kinetically in dry benzene. A mechanism involving a nucleophilic attack of the phosphoryl oxygen on mercuric acetate, to give an intermediate phosphonium ion, is discussed.

FOX and Venezky¹ reported that dialkyl phosphites (1) react with mercuric salts to give dialkyl phosphonylmercuric acetate (2). The reaction may be thought to take place via the nucleophilic

attack of the lone pair of electrons on the phosphorus atoms of (1) on the mercuric acetate.

If this is the case, replacement of (H) in (1) by a heavier group (e.g., $-\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) would compel the reaction with mercuric acetate to proceed in a different way and give another product.

However, we reported² that dialkyl benzylphosphonates (3a) react with mercuric acetate to give (2) at room temperature according to the following mechanism:

rearrangement.⁶ The kinetic data excludes the mechanism proposed in equation (3) as it should be S_N1 in the phosphite only.

References

- 1 R FOX and D VENEZKY, *J Amer Chem Soc*, 1963, **75**, 3968
- 2 W I AWAD, M EL-DREK and E EL-SAWI, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1973, **47**, 4663
- 3 H McCAMBIE, B C SANNDERS, and G STACE *J Chem Soc*, 1945, 380
- 4 J A RIDDICK and E E TOOPS, JR, "Organic Solvents" 2nd Ed, Interscience Publishers, New York, N Y, 1955
- 5 E S GOULD "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", Henry Holt and Co, New York, N Y, 1960, p 182
- 6 (a) A E ARBUSOV, *J Russ Phys Chem Soc.*, 1906, **38**, 687
(b) P C CROFTS, *Quart Rev Chem Soc*, 1950, **12**, 334